

STRATEGIC COMMUNICATION PLAN

TEAL2HEAL WALK OF FEATS NONPROFIT

by

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Introduction

This strategic plan outlines the organization's goals and those of the Whitewater PR Company for each public. It details strategies tailored to those goals for each public while considering the overall objective and key audience. Each strategy is accompanied by a set of specific objectives. Beneath each objective, you will find the associated tactics, including message and media strategies relevant to that tactic. This strategic plan focuses on three key publics: news media, women aged 45 to 69 in the Stevens Point, Wausau, and Mosinee, Wisconsin areas, and students aged 20 to 24 in the Stevens Point area. The plan first reviews the objectives, strategies, and tactics for our key news media audience, followed by our second key public, and lastly, our third key public. The PESO Model represents paid, earned, shared, and owned media.

Overall Goal

By the end of the communication campaign, Teal2Heal will have gained increased awareness and, consequently, more participants in the Walks of Feats Fundraiser. The client's goal is for the communication campaign to recruit 150 participants for the Walk of Feats.

Public I: Print, Radio, and Television Stations Strategies

Strategy I for Print, Radio, and Television News Media:

Teal2Heal has an advantage in that they are the only ovarian cancer nonprofit organization in its area. This could make them a key source of information for journalists in the area, specifically

health journalists. This would make Teal2Heal a valuable and credible source of information for journalists about ovarian cancer. Teal2Heal are specialists in this area, making them have less competition for news coverage about the topic of ovarian cancer nonprofits.

Strategy II for Print, Radio, and Television News Media:

Teal2Heal will leverage the good relationships it builds with journalists to generate media coverage and, therefore, increase awareness of the Walk of Feats Fundraiser.

**Public I: Print, Radio, and Television Stations Objectives and
Tactics**

Print Media

Objective I (Outcome Objective):

To build five new relationships with print media journalists in the Wausau-Rhineland area by September 2024.

Tactic I for Objective I: Pitch letters and emails with tailored messages to journalists from the Wausau Daily Herald, Times Community Newspaper in Mosinee, WI, The Northwoods River News, and Stevens Point Journal to build relationships with them.

- **Message Strategy:** The spokesperson for this message strategy will be the Whitewater PR company. To build credibility about ovarian cancer, use an ethos approach. O’Keefe (2002) defines credibility as “judgments made by a perceiver (e.g., a message recipient) concerning the believability of a communicator.” Focusing

- on the character, ethics, and trustworthiness of the communicator or the source of the information can help build credibility.
- The strategy for using an ethos approach to messaging about ovarian cancer would involve establishing authority, demonstrating honesty and trustworthiness, showing ethical manners, and appealing to shared values to connect with journalists.
 - Read and understand the journalists' work. Let them know the advantage that Teal2Heal has as the leader of ovarian cancer nonprofit work in the area. Inform them that Teal2Heal is the one and only ovarian cancer nonprofit in central Wisconsin. Inform them that Teal2Heal is a resource for them, offering unique insights, data, and commentary on the ovarian cancer nonprofit in the area. Stay in touch with the journalists and be consistent in messaging. Email the journalists with story ideas that are proximately close in geographical range and are relevant, therefore being newsworthy to these journalists.
 - **Media Strategy:** On April 1, 2024, pitch one letter and one email. If you don't receive a response, call the journalist.
 - Maintain the relationship by periodically checking in with updates or news story ideas, even if there isn't an immediate need. Follow up after every published story and ask for feedback or additional information that may help the journalist in the future.
 - This uses the earned media strategy in the Paid, Earned, Social, and Owned (PESO) model. Specifically, it would be best to contact health journalists for the Wausau Daily Herald or a journalist with a vested interest in health matters.

Objective II (Output Objective):

To generate 15 media hits, including a mixture of television news, radio broadcast news, and print news, by September 2024.

Tactic I for Output II: Exclusive handouts for our target journalists at Wausau Daily Herald, Times Community Newspaper in Mosinee, WI, The Northwoods River News, and Stevens Point Journal print news stations.

- **Message Strategy:** The PR professional can more effectively position their story by targeting a specific journalist or news outlet known for covering certain topics or having a particular audience. The story is given exclusively to one journalist or news outlet.
- This exclusivity can make the offer more appealing to the journalist, providing them with a potential scoop or a unique story that no other outlet will have. A suggested story idea with an offer. The news piece is tailored to fit the target news organization's style, tone, and audience.
- This customization can include the story's focus, angle, language, and any multimedia elements accompanying it. Understand the journalist's beat, the topics they cover, and their interests in the industry.
- **Media Strategy:** The exclusive handouts will be sent to Wausau Daily Herald journalists on Monday, June 17, to get a start on the media output for the Walk of Feats Fundraiser.
- They will be sent in July, August, and finally on September 2, weeks before the fundraiser. This will be using the earned category in the PESO model, which is a scheme for categorizing different types of media based on their capabilities, strengths,

and weaknesses they offer us. In this case, earned media has more credibility but a lesser chance that our message will be sent to the public.

Radio Broadcast

Objective I (Outcome Objective):

To build five new relationships with radio broadcast media journalists and Whitewater PR Company/Teal2Heal in the Wausau-Rhineland area by September 2024.

Tactic I for Objective I: Build relationships with journalists from the WFHR-AM 1320, WLBL-AM 930, WSAU-AM 550, WSAU-FM 99.9, WXCO-AM 1230, Wisconsin Public Radio Affiliate, radio channels by letter and email.

- **Message Strategy:** The spokesperson for this message strategy will be the Whitewater PR company. We will use an ethos approach to this messaging to build credibility about ovarian cancer. O’Keefe (2002, as cited in Gass & Seiter, 2018) defines credibility as “judgments made by a perceiver (e.g., a message recipient) concerning the believability of a communicator.” Using an ethos approach to messaging about ovarian cancer to build credibility means focusing on the character, ethics, and trustworthiness of the communicator or the source of the information.
- The strategy for using an ethos approach to messaging about ovarian cancer would involve establishing authority, demonstrating honesty and trustworthiness, showing ethical manners, and appealing to shared values to connect with journalists.
- Read and understand the journalists’ work. Let them know the advantage that Teal2Heal has as the leader of ovarian cancer nonprofit work in the area. Inform them

that Teal2Heal is the one and only ovarian cancer nonprofit in central Wisconsin.

Inform them that Teal2Heal is a resource for them, offering unique insights, data, and commentary on the ovarian cancer nonprofit in the area. Stay in touch with the journalists and be consistent in messaging. Email WFHR-AM 1320 radio channel journalists with story ideas that are proximately close in geographical range and are relevant, therefore being newsworthy to these journalists.

- **Media Strategy:** On April 1, 2024, pitch one letter and email. If you don't receive a response, call the journalist. Maintain the relationship by periodically checking in with updates or news story ideas, even if there isn't an immediate need. Follow up after every published story and ask for feedback or additional information that may help the journalist in the future.
- This is using the earned media strategy in the PESO model. Specifically, it would be best to contact health journalists for the Stevens Point Journal or a journalist with a vested interest in health matters.

Objective II (Output Objective):

To secure five media mentions in radio broadcasts in the Northern Wisconsin area by September 2024.

Tactic I for Objective II: PSA packaged and pre-recorded announcement for WFHR-AM 1320, WLBL-AM 930, WSAU-AM 550, WSAU-FM 99.9, WXCO-AM 1230, and Wisconsin Public Radio Affiliate radio channels.

- **Message Strategy:** Michele Olszewski will be the spokesperson for the PSA pre-recorded announcement. She has experienced ovarian cancer before and ultimately beat the disease, making her a credible source of information.

- Use an appeal in the PSA announcement that matches the audience. There will be an ethos appeal to the journalists when pitching the story to the radio channel.
 - **Media Strategy:** The PSA will be aired during the local news segments, starting in July, then August, and ending on the day of the Walk of Feats Fundraiser, which is in September.
 - This will be using the earned category in the PESO model, which is a scheme for categorizing different types of media based on their capabilities, strengths, and weaknesses they offer us. In this case, earned media has more credibility but a lesser chance that our message will be sent to the public.
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Television Broadcast

Objectives and Tactics

Objective I (Outcome Objective):

To build five new relationships with television broadcast media journalists and Whitewater PR Company/Teal2Heal in the Wausau-Rhineland area by September 2024.

Tactic I for Objective I: Reach out to journalists from WAOW-TV (Channel 9), WJFW-TV (Channel 12, DT Channel 16), and WSAW-TV (Channel 7) television station journalists by letter and email and build relationships with them.

- **Message Strategy:** The spokesperson for this message strategy will be the Whitewater PR company. We will use an ethos approach to this messaging to build credibility about ovarian cancer. O’Keefe (2002) defines credibility as “judgments made by a perceiver (e.g., a message recipient) concerning the believability of a

communicator.” Using an ethos approach to messaging about ovarian cancer to build credibility means focusing on the character, ethics, and trustworthiness of the communicator or the source of the information.

- The strategy for using an ethos approach to messaging about ovarian cancer would involve establishing authority, demonstrating honesty and trustworthiness, showing ethical manners, and appealing to shared values to connect with journalists.
- Read and understand the journalists’ work. Let them know the advantage that Teal2Heal has as the leader of ovarian cancer nonprofit work in the area. Inform them that Teal2Heal is the one and only ovarian cancer nonprofit in central Wisconsin. Inform them that Teal2Heal is a resource for them, offering unique insights, data, and commentary on the ovarian cancer nonprofit in the area. Stay in touch with the journalists and be consistent in messaging. Email WAOW-TV (Channel 9) television station journalists with story ideas that are proximately close in geographical range and are relevant, therefore being newsworthy to these journalists.
- **Media Strategy:** On April 1, 2024, pitch one letter and one email. If you don’t receive a response, call the journalist.
- Maintain the relationship by periodically checking in with updates or news story ideas, even if there isn’t an immediate need. Follow up after every published story and ask for feedback or additional information that may help the journalist in the future.
- This is using the earned media strategy in the PESO model. Specifically, it would be best to contact health journalists for the Stevens Point Journal or a journalist with a vested interest in health matters.

Objective II (Output Objective):

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 - Use an appeal in the PSA announcement that matches the audience. There will be an ethos appeal to the journalists when pitching the story to the television channel.
 - **Media Strategy:** The PSA will be aired during the local news segments, starting in July, then August, and ending on the day of the Walk of Feats Fundraiser, which is in September.
 - This will be using the earned category in the PESO model, which is a scheme for categorizing different types of media based on their capabilities, strengths, and weaknesses they offer us. In this case, earned media has more credibility but a lesser chance that our message will be sent to the public.
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Public II: Women in Mosinee, Wausau, and Stevens Point Ages 45 to 69

Research

Television and digital platforms are key sources of news for the target demographic, particularly women aged 50-64. According to the PEW Research Center (2023), 72% of women in this age group sometimes watch television to get their news. Overall, women are slightly more likely than men to rely on television for news (65% vs. 61%) and use digital devices for news at the same rate (86%). Additionally, 30% of women and 36% of all individuals prefer receiving news from television over radio and print for traditional media (PEW Research Center, 2023, as cited in Situation Analysis). In the United States, Facebook is used by 76% of women, surpassing the usage rates of other platforms such as Instagram (54%), Pinterest (50%), and TikTok (40%). Among adults aged 30 to 49, Facebook's usage rate stands at 75%, exceeding Instagram's 59% and significantly outpacing other social media platforms. Similarly, for the 50 to 64 age group, Facebook's prevalence is notably higher than that of Instagram, Pinterest, and other platforms (PEW Research Center, 2023).

Print Media: Even though this key audience relies less on print than on television for news, we will still send press releases to major newspapers in the area to ensure that our messaging is widely known and repeatedly exposed.

Radio Broadcast: Although this key public does not use radio as much as television to gather their news information, we will still pitch a radio news segment to the key radio stations in the area for the sake of awareness and repeated exposure of the messaging.

Digital: When asked which of these platforms United States adults prefer to get news on, nearly six in ten Americans say they prefer a digital device (58%) more than they prefer TV (27%). Even fewer Americans prefer radio (6%) or print (5%) (PEW Research Center, 2024). In addition, in the United States, Facebook is used by 76% of women, a figure that surpasses usage rates of other social media platforms such as Instagram at 54%, Pinterest at 50%, and TikTok at 40%. It is significantly higher compared to various other platforms (PEW Research Center, 2023). This says that digital tactics are important for us to use for this communication campaign.

Public II Strategies

Strategy I for Public II:

Targeting women aged 45 to 69 in these regions could be particularly effective due to their inherent vulnerability to ovarian cancer (Ovarian Cancer Risk Factors | Risk Factors for Ovarian Cancer, 2024). Given their biological susceptibility, this risk makes the cause more salient to them. Because the cause of fundraising for ovarian cancer, a type of disease that is more risk inherent to this population, the saliency of the issue will be more apparent to them, thus giving Teal2Heal the advantage of reaching this key public. Previous research suggests that certain people give because of sympathy and empathy (Small, Loewenstein & Slovic, 2007; Cryder & Loewenstein, 2008). In other words, people tend to give because they are sympathetic and empathetic toward others. In this case, women tend to feel sympathetic and empathetic toward other women who have ovarian cancer.

Strategy II for Public II:

The advantage that Teal2Heal has is that their fundraiser, Walk of Feats, is family friendly. It involves a race-style competition designed to be inclusive of various demographics, including families with children in strollers, millennials, retired individuals, and everyone in between (L. Olszewski personal communication, retrieved via video, Feb 21, 2024, as cited in Situation Analysis). This advantage means that women can bring their children to the fundraiser, thus increasing total attendance. parents quite commonly instill beliefs, impart values, and model behavior for their children, a phenomenon known as social modeling (Bandura, 1977, as cited in Gass & Seiter, 2018). This social modeling means that the act of charity giving or fundraising attendance will be instilled in children, and they will hopefully come back when they are older and bring their children as well.

Public II Objectives and Tactics**Objective I (Informational Awareness):**

By September 2024, 25% more women aged 45 to 69 who reside in the Wausau, Stevens Point, and Mosinee area will be aware of the Walk of Feats Fundraiser.

Tactic I for Objective I: Television news segment on News 9 WAOW, WJFW-TV (Channel 12, DT Channel 16), and WSAW-TV (Channel 7) about the Walk of Feats Fundraiser while also highlighting the Teal2Heal nonprofit organization.

- **Message Strategy:** Michele Olszewski will act as the spokesperson. This message strategy will use an ethos and pathos appeal. Michele is a survivor of ovarian cancer, making her a credible source of first-hand information about the disease (ethos).

- The way the segment will be set up will induce feelings of sympathy for current ovarian cancer patients (pathos). There will be B-roll shots of ovarian cancer patients (with their consent) in the Aspirus-Wausau hospital, with which Teal2Heal has an existing relationship.
- **Media Strategy for WAOW-TV:** The news segment will air on WAOW-TV local news on weekdays at 6:00 a.m. and 6:00 p.m. This strategy is because women aged 45 to 69 are usually still within their working jobs, if not recently retired. Weekdays at 6:00 a.m. is when most people watch their morning news while getting ready for work, and 6:00 p.m. is when the women get off work and flip on the television.
- On weekends, the news segment, which is local news, will broadcast on News 9 WAOW at 6:00 p.m. and 10:00 p.m.; there is also a morning broadcast titled “Wake Up Wisconsin Weekend” at 6:00 a.m. on weekends, which may include local news segments.
- **Media Strategy for WJFW-TV (Channel 12, DT Channel 16):** The news segment will air on WJFW-TV (Channel 12, DT Channel 16) at 10:00 p.m. on Saturdays under the program title “Newswatch 12 at 10 p.m. Saturday.” This segment highlights local news.
- **Media Strategy for WSAW-TV (Channel 7) at NewsChannel 7:** This news segment will air on WSAW-TV (Channel 7) at NewsChannel 7 at 6:00 p.m. and again at 10:00 p.m. on weekdays. It will also air on weekends at 6:00 p.m. on Saturday and Sunday. This is when they highlight local news (Programming Schedule, 2024, as cited in Situation Analysis).

- This would fall under the earned media type in the PESO model, which is a scheme for categorizing different types of media based on their capabilities, strengths, and weaknesses they offer us. In this case, earned media has more credibility but a lesser chance that our message will be sent to the public because it is uncontrolled media. However, by building relationships with journalists, our chances of our message reaching the news are a lot higher.

Tactic II for Objective I: Press release about the Walk of Feats Fundraiser and highlighting the Teal2Heal nonprofit organization to the Wausau Daily Herald, Times Community Newspaper, The Northwoods River News, Stevens Point Journal.

- **Message Strategy:** Michele Olszewski will act as the spokesperson, and the press release will include two quotes from her. This message strategy will mostly use an ethos appeal. Michele is a survivor of ovarian cancer, so she is a credible source of first-hand information about the disease. The press release will explain the Walk of Feats Fundraiser and the Teal2Heal nonprofit organization.
- **Media Strategy:** The press release will be sent out in July, as the September Walk of Feats Fundraiser approaches. Another press release will be sent out two weeks before the September Walk of Feats fundraiser. Strategic journalists will be used.

Tactic III for Objective I: Radio news segment on WFHR-AM 1320, WLBL-AM 930, WSAU-AM 550, WSAU-FM 99.9, WXCO-AM 1230, Wisconsin Public Radio Affiliate about the Walk of Feats Fundraiser while also highlighting the Teal2Heal nonprofit organization.

- **Message Strategy:** Michele Olszewski will act as the spokesperson. This message strategy will use an ethos and pathos appeal. Michele is a survivor of ovarian cancer, making her a credible source of first-hand information about the disease (ethos).
- The way the segment will be set up will induce feelings of sympathy for current ovarian cancer patients (pathos). There will be B-roll shots of ovarian cancer patients (with their consent) in the Aspirus-Wausau hospital, with which Teal2Heal has an existing relationship. The main key points will include the Teal2Heal organization and the Walk of Feats Fundraiser.
- **Media Strategy:** The news segment will air during the local news segment on the radio station. It will air once weekly from July to September, when the Walk of Feats Fundraiser takes place.

Tactic IV for Objective I: A paid digital advertisement on Facebook about the Teal2Heal Nonprofit Organization.

- **Message Strategy:** Michele Olszewski will act as the spokesperson. This message strategy will use an ethos and pathos appeal. Michele is a survivor of ovarian cancer, making her a credible source of first-hand information about the disease (ethos).
- Michele will explain the Walk of Feats Fundraiser and why it's important to attend. The messaging will emphasize the importance of women aged 45 to 69 getting ovarian cancer, making the cause of the Walk of Feats Fundraiser more important.
- **Media Strategy:** The Facebook advertisement will air for two weeks, once every other month until August, for a total of three months over the course of six months. This will give time for the Walk of Feats fundraiser's shared social media tactic to take over in September.

- This would fall under the paid media type in the PESO model, which is a scheme for categorizing different types of media based on their capabilities, strengths, and weaknesses they offer us. In this case, paid media has less credibility but a guaranteed chance that our message will be sent to the public because it is controlled media.

Objective II (Motivational Opinion):

By September 2024, 20% more women aged 45 to 60 who reside in the Wausau, Stevens Point, and Mosinee areas will have the opinion that ovarian cancer is an important cause.

Tactic I for Objective I: A shared video on Teal2Heal’s Facebook page.

- **Message Strategy:** This message’s spokesperson will be a current ovarian cancer patient. This appeals to both ethos and pathos because the patient is a first-hand source of information, having recently recovered from the disease. The pathos appeal will be heightened by feelings of empathy and sympathy from the key public of women aged 45 to 69.
- A short interview with a current ovarian cancer patient who has received help from the Teal2Heal organization will be part of the segment. The patient will talk a little bit about what they have been going through and how Teal2Heal made them feel better and more supported through their recovery journey. There will be emotional music in the background of the video. The video will explain that the Walk of Feats Fundraiser is the main source of donations for ovarian cancer patients, like the one in the video.
- **Media Strategy:** Use of hashtags such as #survivor, #ovariancancer, #cancersurvivor will be used along with the message. The video will tag all other ovarian cancer organizations on Facebook. The main strategy is to tag the surrounding hospitals in the Wausau, Stevens Point, and Mosinee areas, including the Aspirus-Wausau Hospital,

which already has a working relationship with Teal2Heal and other hospitals in the area. However, the organizations that will be tagged will not be limited to the Wisconsin area. As many other ovarian cancer organizations as possible will be tagged as well.

- This would fall under the shared media type in the PESO model, which is a scheme for categorizing different types of media based on their capabilities, strengths, and weaknesses they offer us. In this case, shared media has more credibility but a lesser chance that the message will be sent to the public because it is uncontrolled media.

Objective III (Behavioral Outcome):

By September 2024, 75 women aged 45 to 69 in the Stevens Point, Wausau, and Mosinee, WI areas will attend the Walk of Feats Fundraiser with their families. This will be measured by using a sign-in sheet at the fundraiser.

Tactic I for Objective III: Create an email list by using an email list signup on Facebook. Use the email to continuously remind the key public of the dates of the Walk of Feats Fundraiser to push them to go.

- **Message Strategy:** The email with the fundraiser dates will be informational. It will include a photograph of Teal2Heal’s spokesperson, Michele Olszewski, and a blurb at the top of “important news and dates” with the fundraiser dates included.
- **Media Strategy:** The email will be a one-page newsletter. The remainder of the Walk of Feats fundraiser dates will be included in every newsletter, which will be sent out once monthly until the event in September 2024. (The newsletter will continue to be sent out monthly thereafter.)

Tactic II for Objective I: Create an email newsletter for the key public about updates and news on ovarian cancer and Teal2Heal. Use the newsletter that has already been created and the email list that will be created through Facebook.

- **Message Strategy:** The newsletter's appeal will be mostly informational, with a mixture of ethos (the spokesperson's credibility) and pathos (the emotional appeal). The emotional appeal will include feelings of sympathy and empathy. The email newsletter will include write-ups and interviews with current ovarian cancer patients, doctors, and families who have been affected by the disease.
- **Media Strategy:** The email newsletter will be sent out once a month, on the first Monday at 9 a.m. The newsletter will be A/B tested to ensure that this day and time work; if it does not, the date and time will be changed to ensure that most women aged 45 to 69 are opening the newsletter.

Objective IV (Behavioral Outcome):

By September 2025, 75 women aged 45 to 69 and their families in the Stevens Point, Wausau, and Mosinee, WI, areas will re-attend the Walk of Feats Fundraiser. This will be measured using a sign-in sheet at the fundraiser.

Tactic I for Objective IV: Have an email sign-in sheet at the Walk of Feats fundraiser.

Attendees must sign in with their emails to enter the games.

- **Message Strategy:** This is purely an informational behavior message strategy. The email list will be a way to enter the race.
- **Media Strategy:** The emails entered or written down at the Walk of Feats fundraiser will be saved and added to the master email list. The master email list will include a

newsletter sent to the key public once a month, specifically on the first Monday of the month, at 9 a.m.

Tactic II for Objective IV: Facebook posts will be made about the turnout for the Walk of Feats fundraiser, updates on the Fundraiser, and the dates of the next Fundraiser.

- **Message Strategy:** The message appeal for these Facebook posts will be exciting, happy, and empowering.
- **Media Strategy:** Professional photographs of people enjoying the Walk of Feats Fundraiser will be shared a week after the event. Photographs of women aged 45 to 69 and their children will be shared to show that people of any age can attend and enjoy the Walk of Feats Fundraiser.
- **Justification:** A way in which images persuade is through syntactic indeterminacy (Gass & Seiter, 2018). A persuader can also foster subtle associations through images without making the associations explicit in words (Gass & Seiter, 2018). In other words, if the photographs on Facebook show people enjoying the Walk of Feats fundraiser, they will believe that they will have fun participating in it as well.

Objective V (Behavioral Outcome):

By September 2025, Teal2Heal’s Facebook page will have an additional 75 followers, most of whom are women aged 45 to 69 in the Stevens Point, Wausau, and Mosinee, WI, areas.

Tactic I for Objective V: A Facebook giveaway will be offered at the Walk of Feats Fundraiser in September 2024.

- **Message Strategy:** The message appeal will be exciting and thrilling. By following Teal2Heal on Facebook, the key public will be kept aware of news about ovarian cancer, updates on Teal2Heal, and the next dates of the Walk of Feats Fundraiser.

- **Media Strategy:** At the sign-in table at the Walk of Feats fundraiser, a volunteer will explain to each participant that they have the chance to win a prize basket if they follow Teal2Heal on Facebook. They will be given a small sheet of paper on which they will have to put down their Facebook name. Then, they will have to follow Teal2Heal on Facebook in order to be entered and win the prize basket. The prize basket will include items that are teal-colored, including a teal-colored sherpa blanket, a teal-colored tumbler mug, a color-changing Himalayan salt lamp, and a teal-colored candle.
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Public III: Students in Stevens Point at UW-Stevens Point and Technical Schools Ages 20-24

Research

In Stevens Point, Wisconsin, which has a population of 25,666, young adults aged 20 to 24 make up 20.7% of the total population, largely due to the presence of the University of Wisconsin-Stevens Point. According to the U.S. Census Bureau, 62.4% of individuals aged 18 to 24 in Stevens Point have pursued education beyond high school, either through some college experience or earning an associate degree, indicating a significant portion is likely enrolled in college. College students in Stevens Point are characterized by strong educational ties, digital savviness, and increased social activism (Broido, 2000). Additionally, a large percentage of college-aged adults nationwide are active on social media, with 78% using Instagram, 67% using Facebook, and 65% using Snapchat (Pew Research Center, 2024).

Public III Students Strategies

Strategy I for Public III:

According to the U.S. Census Bureau, there is a significant increase in the young adult population in Stevens Point, especially those between 20 and 24 years old, representing 20.7% of the population or 5,284 total people (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). This demographic of college students is often looking for ways to engage in community service, social activities, and causes they care about. For example, college students have long been involved in efforts to develop more just and equitable societies (Broido, 2000). The advantage here is that Teal2Heal is a nonprofit organization that has a good cause behind it, thereby increasing its importance to this key public.

Strategy II for Public III:

There is a large number of people aged 20 to 24 in Stevens Point, Wisconsin, with a population of 25,666, constituting 20.7% of its total population (as cited in Situation Analysis). This demographic trend is largely driven by the presence of the University of Wisconsin-Stevens Point in the area, attracting a significant portion of individuals in this age group. This could be used to Teal2Heal's advantage by targeting this age group, which is the largest group of people in the area. This, in turn, would make it a great key public to get more attendance to the Walk of Feats Fundraiser.

Public III Students Objectives and Tactics

Objective I (Informational Awareness Outcome):

Increase awareness of the Teal2Heal organization and Walk of Feats Fundraiser by 25% among students aged 20 to 24 in the Stevens Point geographical area by September 2024.

Tactic I for Objective I: Tabling at the University of Wisconsin-Stevens Point and Mid-State Technical College, Stevens Point Campus.

- **Message Strategy:** The appeal of the message will be informational while also tapping into ethos (credibility) and pathos (emotional appeal). The spokesperson for this message will be an ovarian cancer survivor volunteering at the booth. The volunteer will offer personal stories to the students who come to the booth. The emotional aspect will be formed of sympathy and empathy. This tactic will use the strategy of students wanting to do something good with a good cause behind it.
- **Media Strategy for Objective Ten Tactic One:** The table will have a teal tablecloth and a sign for Teal2Heal. Small trinkets, mostly items with Teal2Heal and Walk of Feats Fundraiser logos, will be available for students to grab for free. These items will include ChapSticks and key rings.

Tactic II for Objective I: A series of shared Instagram reels on the Teal2Heal Instagram account.

- **Message Strategy:** The message appeal of these Instagram reels will tap into the pathos appeal. There will be an emotional response in the audience to empower them to do something good for a good cause. There will be messages from current ovarian cancer patients, with their consent.

- **Media Strategy:** Use of hashtags such as #survivor, #ovariancancer, #cancersurvivor will be used along with the message. The video will tag all other ovarian cancer organizations on Facebook. The main strategy is to tag the surrounding hospitals in the Wausau, Stevens Point, and Mosinee areas, including the Aspirus-Wausau Hospital, which already has a working relationship with Teal2Heal and other hospitals in the area. However, the organizations that will be tagged will not be limited to the Wisconsin area. As many other ovarian cancer organizations as possible will be tagged as well.
- One reel will be shared once per week until August 2024. The reels will be a “series,” so they will have similar background music, similar pathos appeal, and similar messaging.
- This would fall under the shared media type in the PESO model, which is a scheme for categorizing different types of media based on their capabilities, strengths, and weaknesses they offer us. In this case, shared media has more credibility but a lesser chance that the message will be sent to the public because it is uncontrolled media.
- Post-event socializing will also help with shared media, promising effective promotion via social media for ovarian cancer support. Engaging this group through digital channels they frequently use will enhance the likelihood of a successful event.

Objective II (Motivational Opinion):

By September 2024, 25% of students aged 20 to 24 in the Stevens Point, Wisconsin, area will believe that ovarian cancer is an important and salient cause.

Tactic I for Objective II: A series of shared Instagram posts on the Teal2Heal Instagram account.

- **Message Strategy:** The appeal of these Instagram posts will include mostly ethos appeal, which will build credibility. The posts will include the spokesperson Michele Olszewski,

who will be the one “talking” in the descriptions of the posts. The posts will include facts about how serious ovarian cancer is so that they will become salient to the audience.

- **Media Strategy:** There will be one post every week, ongoing. The post will use a graphic and text for the “fact of the week.”
- Hashtags such as #survivor, #ovariancancer, and #cancersurvivor will be used along with the message. The video will tag all other ovarian cancer organizations on Facebook. The main strategy is to tag the surrounding hospitals in the Wausau, Stevens Point, and Mosinee areas, including the Aspirus-Wausau Hospital, which already has a working relationship with Teal2Heal and other hospitals in the area. However, the organizations that will be tagged will not be limited to the Wisconsin area. As many other ovarian cancer organizations as possible will be tagged as well.
- This would fall under the shared media type in the PESO model, which is a scheme for categorizing different types of media based on their capabilities, strengths, and weaknesses they offer us. In this case, shared media has more credibility but a lesser chance that the message will be sent to the public because it is uncontrolled media.

Tactic II for Objective II: A series of shared Instagram stories on the Teal2Heal Instagram account.

- **Message Strategy:** The spokesperson, Michele Olszewski, will post Instagram stories explaining facts, Q&A, and other details about ovarian cancer and its seriousness. This will make the cause important to the key public.
- **Media Strategy:** There will be one post of Michele Olszewski speaking on Teal2Heal’s Instagram story every day.

- The stories can vary from what goes on behind the scenes at Teal2Heal, facts about ovarian cancer, personal stories from Michele Olszewski, stories from doctors and nurses, and stories from current ovarian cancer patients.
- Hashtags such as #survivor, #ovariancancer, and #cancersurvivor will be used along with the message. The video will tag all other ovarian cancer organizations on Facebook. The main strategy is to tag the surrounding hospitals in the Wausau, Stevens Point, and Mosinee areas, including the Aspirus-Wausau Hospital, which already has a working relationship with Teal2Heal and other hospitals in the area. However, the organizations that will be tagged will not be limited to the Wisconsin area. As many other ovarian cancer organizations as possible will be tagged as well.
- This would fall under the shared media type in the PESO model, which is a scheme for categorizing different types of media based on their capabilities, strengths, and weaknesses they offer us. In this case, shared media has more credibility but a lesser chance that the message will be sent to the public because it is uncontrolled media.

Objective III (Behavioral Outcome):

By September 12, 2024, the day of the Walk of Feats Fundraiser, the number of participants aged 20 to 24 will increase by 50.

Tactic I for Objective III: Hand out a voucher at the tables when tabling at the colleges. This voucher will be for “attend and bring one person for free.”

- **Message Strategy:** This is an informational message strategy.
- **Media Strategy:** The strategy behind this is to still get donations, but it will increase the total attendance among this population. College students usually have clubs, groups, and

friends, so this will motivate them to attend the Walk of Feats Fundraiser and bring someone with them, thereby increasing attendance.

Tactic II for Objective III: Offer college clubs and organizations the opportunity for community service by volunteering at the Walk of Feats Fundraiser.

- **Message Strategy:** This message strategy will empower student organizations to make a difference for a good cause.
- **Media Strategy:** Organize with the leaders of the student organizations and the Student Activities and Involvement teams at the colleges to provide this opportunity to college student organizations.

Objective IV (Behavioral Outcome):

By September 2025, 75 students aged 20 to 24 in the Stevens Point, WI area will re-attend the Walk of Feats Fundraiser. This will be measured by using a sign-in sheet at the fundraiser.

Tactic I for Objective IV: Have an email sign-in sheet at the Walk of Feats fundraiser.

Attendees must sign in with their emails to enter the games.

- **Message Strategy for Objective Thirteen Tactic One:** This is purely an informational behavior message strategy. The email list will be a way to enter the race.
- **Media Strategy for Objective Thirteen Tactic One:** The emails that are entered or written down at the Walk of Feats fundraiser will be saved and added to the master email list. The master email list will include an email newsletter that is sent out to the key public once a month, on the first Monday of the month, at 9 a.m.

Tactic II for Objective IV: The newsletter will also be shared on Instagram to reach this key public.

- **Message Strategy:** The newsletter's appeal will be primarily informational, with a mixture of ethos (credibility of the spokesperson) and pathos (emotional appeal). The emotional appeal will include feelings of sympathy and empathy. The email newsletter will include writeups and interviews with current ovarian cancer patients, doctors, and families who have been affected by the disease.
- **Media Strategy:** For this key public, the email list will also include an option for participants and volunteers to put their Instagram handles down. The email newsletter will be shared on Instagram once a month, on the first Monday at 9 a.m.

Objective V (Behavioral Outcome):

By September 2025, Teal2Heal's Instagram page will have accumulated an additional 75 followers, of whom are students aged 20 to 24 in the Stevens Point area.

Tactic I for Objective V: An Instagram giveaway will be offered at the booth at UW-Stevens Point and Mid-State Technical College, Stevens Point Campus.

- **Message Strategy:** The message appeal will be exciting and thrilling. By following Teal2Heal on Instagram, the key public will be kept aware of news about ovarian cancer, updates on Teal2Heal, and the next dates of the Walk of Feats Fundraiser.
- **Media Strategy:** At the sign-in table at the Walk of Feats fundraiser, a volunteer will explain to each participant that they have the chance to win a prize basket if they follow Teal2Heal on Instagram. They will be given a small sheet of paper on which they will have to put down their Facebook name. Then, they will have to follow Teal2Heal on Instagram in order to be entered and win the prize basket. The prize basket will include items that are teal-colored, including a teal-colored sherpa blanket, a teal-colored tumbler mug, a color-changing Himalayan salt lamp, and a teal-colored candle.

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